

Validation of the typology and classification system in Bulgaria for assessment the ecological status of surface water bodies of categories “river”, “lake” and “transitional waters”

Final Report

Annex 6

Methods for the analysis of BQEs, reference conditions and the ecological status classification system in the target types of surface waters

FISH

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Abbreviations

BFBI-L5	Fish Based Index (Lake type L5)
BQE	Biological quality elements
EQR	Ecological quality ratio
EP	Ecological potential
ES	Ecological status
EU	European Union
GEP	Good ecological potential
GES	Good ecological status
IC	Intercalibration
MEP	Maximum ecological potential
nEQR	Normalised ecological quality ratio
PI	Pressure Index
SWB	Surface water body
TsBRI	The multi-metric Type Specific Fish Based Index
BFBILE	Bulgarian Fish Based Index for Assessing the Ecological Quality of Lentic Ecosystems

1 Introduction and objectives according to the ToR

Fish is one of the biological quality elements (BQE) required for the classification of ecological status and ecological potential of surface water bodies (SWB) under the Water Framework Directive (WFD). It is relevant for lakes/reservoirs and rivers.

For rivers, the multi-metric Type Specific Fish Based Index (TsBRI) has proven a well-working and useful index in Bulgaria for the river types R2, R4, R7, R8 & R14 and has been intercalibrated within the Cross GIG “Danubian Group” and “Mediterranean Group” (Apostolou *et al.* 2016a; Apostolou *et al.* 2016b; Decision 2018/229/EU 2018).

For lakes, a Fish Based Index (BFBI-L5) for ecological classification and monitoring was developed for only one type of lake in Bulgaria so far, the Type L5/L-EC-1 - Natural Riparian Lakes (Pehlivanov *et al.* 2016, Ordinance H4 from 2012, as amended in 2020 (MoEW 2020)).

Activity 6.3 of the ToR requires the development/validation of the classification system for the assessment of the ecological status of the following river and lake types that have not yet been included in the intercalibration: (R1, R3, R5, R9, R10, R11, R12, R13, R14 (without the sub-type, corresponding to the Mediterranean type RM-2), R15, R16, L1, L2, L3, L4, L6, L7, L8, L9, L10).

Activity 6.4 of the ToR addresses the classification system for assessment of the ecological potential of heavily modified water bodies and includes the remaining lake types L11 – L17.

The tasks include:

- 1) An evaluation of existing classification methods and types to be considered
- 2) An evaluation of available data on fish and relevant pressures
- 3) Calculations of pressure-response relationships
- 4) A definition of reference conditions and reference values for the selected metric(s)
- 5) Setting of class boundaries

2 Available Data on Fish and Pressures

2.1 Monitoring sites

In 2020, a total of 220 sites were sampled according to WFD requirements, 141 sites were located in lotic (within 14 national types) and 83 in lentic ecosystems (within 17 national types). Some river sites were dry at the time of sampling and at some heavy polluted sites a complete absence of fish fauna was registered.

Rivers

For 109 sites a nEQR value was calculated based on the TsBRI. These nEQR values derive from 13 different surface waterbody (SWB) types (Table 1, list of types see Data annex chapter 9.1). The number of sites per type varied. In type R09, for example, just three sites have a nEQR value, whereas 16 sites were sampled in type R03. The consolidated data set includes data from 109 river monitoring sites sampled between early June and November 2020.

Table 1. Distribution of river sampling sites among different SWB types (see Data annex chapter 9.1).

SWB Type	R01	R03	R05	R07	R08	R09	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16	total
# of sites	7	16	10	4	4	3	10	15	13	9	7	5	6	109

Lakes

Sampling was done in a total of 83 lake/reservoir sites in 14 SWB types, within the year 2020 (Table 2). The consolidated data set includes data from 49 lake/reservoir monitoring sites belonging to 14 lake types sampled between early June and November 2020.

Table 2. Distribution of lake/reservoir sampling sites among different SWB types.

SWB Type	L01	L02	L03	L04	L06	L07	L08	L11	L12	L13	L14	L15	L16	L17	total
# of sites	6	5	5	3	3	3	5	5	2	4	2	3	2	1	49

2.2 Hydromorphological Pressures

Table 3 shows the pressures at lakes and rivers used for the evaluation of the pressure – response relationship of the Bulgarian fish indices. Details on the hydromorphological pressures have been presented earlier as Annex 1 of the 5th Bimonthly Progress Report (*cf* chapter 2.3.3 in the Final Report).

In the pressure – response relationships, both single metrics and the sum of all pressures (abbreviated below as SUM_Pres), and weighted combinations of different pressures were tested.

Table 3. List of used pressures for lakes and rivers at the sampling site (in brackets: abbreviations used below).

Parameter	Lakes	Rivers
Impoundment	+	+
Abstraction	+	+
Hydropeaking	+	+
Channelisation	+	+
Lateral dams at the sampling site (Dams_site)	+	+
Lateral dams at the sampling segment (Dams_seg)	+	+
Alteration of riparian vegetation at the sampling site (VegRip_site)	+	+
Alteration of riparian vegetation at the sampling segment (VegRip_seg)	+	+
Habitat alteration at the sampling site (HabAlt_site)	+	+
Habitat alteration at the sampling segment (HabAlt_seg)	+	+
(Assumed) toxic impact (Toxic)	+	+
Temperature Modification	+	+
Migration Barriers	+	+
Fish introduction	+	
Aquaculture	+	
Invasive species	+	
Water level fluctuation	+	

2.3 Corine Landcover

From the Corine landcover (CLC) data that were available at SWB scale level, the CLC class 1 (artificial) as well as the intensive and extensive agriculture in the catchment area was used, in all cases as a relative proportion of the total area of the SWB watershed.

3 Rivers

3.1 Significant impact factors

3.1.1 Hydromorphological pressures

Hydromorphological pressure variables preponderantly showed a significant correlation within the normalised ecological quality ratio (nEQR) calculated from the TsBRI (Table 4).

Table 4. Spearman-correlation coefficient between the hydromorphological pressures and the normalised ecological quality ratio (nEQR).

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
Anthr_chem	-0.540	< 0.001	***
HabAlter_seg	-0.506	< 0.001	***
Channelisation	-0.446	< 0.001	***
Anthr_landscape	-0.445	< 0.001	***
HabAlter_site	-0.440	< 0.001	***
VegRiparian_seg	-0.434	< 0.001	***
VegRiparian_site	-0.351	< 0.001	***
Toxic	-0.343	< 0.001	***
Dams_seg	-0.293	< 0.01	**
Abstraction	-0.228	< 0.05	*
Dams_site	-0.226	< 0.05	*
Hydropeaking	-0.070	ns	ns
Impoundment	-0.034	ns	ns
Migr_Barriers	-0.027	ns	ns
Sum of pressures	-0.629	< 0.001	***

In detail, the Spearman's correlation analysis (tested two-sided) shows a weak correlation ($R < \pm 0.1$) between nEQR and the pressures: Impoundment, Migration Barriers and Hydropeaking (not significant). Furthermore, it shows a medium correlation ($R > \pm 0.1 < \pm 0.5$) between nEQR and the Pressures: Water Abstraction, Dams segment (Dykes), Dams site (Dykes), Channelization, Riparian Vegetation segment, Riparian Vegetation site, Habitat Alteration site, Toxic, Anthropogenic alteration (landscape), CLC1, CLC2int (significant to highly significant).

Additionally, it shows a strong correlation ($R > \pm 0.5$) between nEQR and the pressures: Habitat Alteration segment & Anthropogenic chemistry.

3.1.2 Corine landcover (CLC)

Another analysis focused on landuse, both CLC classes, correlated significant with the nEQR (Table 5).

Table 5. Spearman-correlation coefficients between the Corine landcover and normalised ecological quality ratio (nEQR).

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
CLC2	-0.367	< 0.001	***
CLC1	-0.357	< 0.001	***

The analyses of hydromorphological pressures and Corine landcover data showed a sensitivity of the biological metrics against anthropogenic pressures.

3.2 Calculation of the fish index TsBRI

The calculation follows the existing method as developed earlier and successfully intercalibrated in 2016 (Apostolou *et al.* 2016a; Apostolou *et al.* 2016b). It is based on eight metrics (Table 6).

Table 6. Metrics used in the TsBRI and correspondence to the WFD obligatory criteria.

Metrics in TsBRI	WFD Criteria, referred to the parameter
Total species number	Taxonomic composition
Total abundance/biomass	Abundance
Type-specific species	Age structure + Disturbance
Predatory species (only for some national types)	Age structure + Disturbance
Invasive species	Age structure + Disturbance
Migratory species	Age structure + Disturbance
Sensitive species	Age structure + Disturbance/Sensitive taxa
Dominant species	Age structure + Disturbance/Sensitive taxa

The index is calculated as:
$$\frac{\text{total sum of sampling scores}}{\text{total sum of reference scores}}$$

The key elements of the assessment method are described in detail in Mihov (2010) and Belkinova *et al.* (2013). Seven metrics are used, each of them with points from 0 to a maximum of 10, 15 or 20 (depending on the metric). The Type Specific Bulgarian Fish Index (TsBRI) is calculated as the sum of the points (Table 7).

Table 7. Brief description of the algorithm of the respective metrics used in TsBRI.

Metrics	Max. points	Categories per metric
1. Community structure of the indicative species/Community structure of the predatory species (only for some river types)	10	3
2. Community structure of the migratory species	20	5
3. Community structure and comparative abundance of the sensitive species	20	5
4. Tolerance of the dominant species	20	4
5. Total abundance and biomass per unit area	0	6
6. Comparative abundance of alien species	15	5
7. Total number of species	15	25
Total points = TsBRI	100	

For the final assessment, the EQR is calculated based on type-specific reference values for the TsBRI. These were derived from reference coenoses adapted for each river type and fish zone (see Data annex chapter 9.2). Finally, the EQR is converted to normalized EQR values (nEQR) to get class boundaries at 0.2, 0.4, 0.6 and 0.8 (see Annex 4 “Benthic Invertebrates” of the Final Report). According to the obtained results, the status is classified in one to five classes, as required by the WFD.

To guarantee a harmonised assessment and to minimise errors during data input and calculation, the whole calculation process is performed automatically in an Excel spreadsheet developed during this project.

3.3 Pressure – Response Relationship

3.3.1 Pressure Index calculation

To create a Pressure Index (PI), the Pressure Index as from 2016 intercalibration exercise (IC) was used and adapted. The pressure index (PI) includes the weighted sum of defined hydromorphological pressures, (assumed) toxic impact and Corine landcover. The selected parameters were chosen by evaluating their significance in the correlation with the biological response metrics.

The PI for Rivers is calculated as the sum of the weighted pressures as follows:

$$PI = migration + hydro-peaking + water\ abstraction + temperature\ alteration + channelization * 2 + riparian\ vegetation\ alteration\ (site) + habitat\ alteration\ (site) * 2 + dykes\ [=dams] * 2 + toxicity * 10 + acidification + Anthropogenic\ impact\ (landscape) * 2 + CLC\ urban / 5 + CLC\ intensive\ agriculture / 20$$

For the WB Types “R03” and “R05” additionally:

$$PI_{(R3\&R5)} = PI + water\ abstraction + habitat\ alteration\ (site)$$

3.3.2 Relationship between pressure index (PI) and nEQR

The pressure – response relationship with PI as independent variable and nEQR as dependent variable is shown in Figure 1. The calculated result is highly significant and explains of 42% of the total variance (R^2 of 0.42 – which corresponds to a correlation coefficient of 0.64). The regression model exceeds the recommended r value (0.5) according to the CIS Guidance Documents on IC. The outcome of the regression model is shown in Table 8.

Figure 1. Correlation between the pressure index and the nEQR based on the TsBRI.

Table 8. Linear regression model Pressure Index PI vs nEQR calculated from TsBRI.

Linear regression model: Biotic Index nEQR ~ Pressure Index PI

```
Call:
lm(formula = nEQR ~ PI, data = data)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.66614 -0.14401  0.03538  0.17820  0.45093

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  0.835300   0.038124  21.910 < 2e-16 ***
PI          -0.018798   0.002158  -8.713 4.11e-14 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.2346 on 107 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.415,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.4095
F-statistic: 75.91 on 1 and 107 DF,  p-value: 4.112e-14
```

The regression analysis separated by the SWB types is showing differentiated results (Figure 2). The types R05, R10 and R12 show a considerably weaker response of the nEQR to an increasing PI. For R08, the nEQR hardly reacts to the PI. Type R09 shows a weak reaction, at the same time the results already appear clearly outside of the expected range (small number of values). It should be mentioned, however, that the number of sites for each WB Type is rather low and hence the statistical analyses is weakened.

Figure 2: Regression plot - Pressure Index and nEQR by SWB types.

Figure 3: Boxplot of nEQR by SWB type.

Figure 4: Boxplot of PI by SWB type.

As the hierarchical structure of the data set implies, the boxplots of nEQR and PI indicate a varying distribution among SWB types (Figure 3 & Figure 4). Furthermore, the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) is pointing on a group effect and therefore mixed effect models were created. Operating model comparison (using AIC, BIC and bayes factor) results in random intercept models as the best supported models (Figure 5). The calculations were carried out in *R* with the package *lme4* (Bates *et al.* 2015; Bates *et al.* 2012). The fit for the model R^2 improves slightly from 0.42 to 0.46.

Table 9. Linear mixed model with Pressure Index as fixed variable and SWB type as random factor.

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

Formula: nEQR ~ PI + (1 | WBType)

Data: data

REML criterion at convergence: 6.2

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.9434	-0.5836	0.1252	0.6627	2.2235

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
WBType	(Intercept)	0.005032	0.07094
	Residual	0.051043	0.22593

Number of obs: 109, groups: WBType, 13

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	0.851422	0.043184	19.716
PI	-0.019166	0.002186	-8.765

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

	(Intr)
adptd_PI_hy	-0.717

Figure 5: Random intercept linear model.

Table 10. Type-specific offsets calculated to derive the cbTsBRI (= corrected TsBRI after continuous benchmarking, see Annex 2 “Benthic Invertebrates”) in BG river types (rounded to 3 digits).

Type	Offset	Type	Offset	Type	Offset
R01	0.055	R09	0.083	R14	-0.065
R03	-0.057	R10	0.026	R15	-0.027
R05	-0.059	R11	0.009	R16	0.006
R07	0.026	R12	-0.022		
R08	0.040	R13	-0.014		

The statistical analyses show a significant and strong response of fish communities on anthropogenic pressures (PI), with slightly differences according to different WB Types.

4 Lakes

4.1 Significant impact factors

4.1.1 Pressures used for analyses

Used pressure variables partially showed a significant correlation within the normalised ecological quality ratio (nEQR) (Table 11). The calculation of the nEQR was done in the same way as for TsBRI and the indices of the other BQE. For the lake index see next section (chapter 4.2).

Table 11. Spearman-correlation coefficient between the used pressures and the normalised ecological quality ratio (nEQR) calculated from the index BFBILE.

Physical-chemical parameter	Spearman correlation	p	significance
Migr_Barriers	-0.439	< 0.01	**
HabAlter_seg	-0.425	< 0.01	**
fish.introductions	-0.351	< 0.05	*
HabAlter_site	-0.330	< 0.05	*
VegRiparian_seg	-0.314	< 0.05	*
Impoundment	-0.275	ns	ns
Invasive.species	-0.238	ns	ns
VegRiparian_site	-0.156	ns	ns
Water_level_fluct	-0.126	ns	ns
Aquaculture	-0.112	ns	ns
Hydropeaking	NA	ns	ns
TempMod	NA	ns	ns
Toxic	NA	ns	ns
Sum of pressures	-0.587	< 0.01	**

In detail, the Spearman's correlation analysis (tested two-sided) shows a medium correlation ($R > \pm 0.1 < \pm 0.5$) between nEQR and the pressures: Aquaculture, Water lever fluctuation, Riparian Vegetation site, Invasive species, and Impoundment (not significant). Furthermore, it shows a medium correlation ($R > \pm 0.1 < \pm 0.5$) between nEQR and the pressures: Riparian Vegetation segment, Habitat Alteration site, Fish introductions, Habitat Alteration segment and Migration (significant to highly significant). Additionally, it shows a strong correlation ($R > \pm 0.5$) between nEQR and the sum of all pressures.

The analyses of pressures data showed a sensitivity of the combined biological metrics against anthropogenic pressures.

4.2 Calculation of the fish index BFBILE

The calculation of the Bulgarian Fish Based Index for Assessing the Ecological Quality of Lentic Ecosystems (BFBILE) was newly designed in this project. It follows the principles of the TsBRI and was adapted according to the specific fish-ecological conditions in lentic ecosystems such as lakes and reservoirs.

The metrics used and the type-specific scores are summarised in Table 12. The EQR and nEQR calculation is carried out in the same way as for the river index TsBRI.

Table 12. Metrics used in the calculation of the BFBILE. The scores give the maximum values under reference conditions as derived from the reference communities.

METRICS	L01	L02	L03	L04A	L04B	L06	L07	L08	L11	L12	L13	L14	L15	L16	L17
Predatory + carp abundance	10	10	10	5	5	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	5
Predatory + carp biomass	10	10	10	5	5	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	5
Sensitive	20	20	20	10	0	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	10
Tolerant	20	20	20	10	10	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	10
Alien	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Total abundance	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total biomass	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Rheophilic/Migratory OR Marine/Brackish	20	20	20	0	0	20	10	10	20	20	20	20	20	20	10
Total species to area (adjustment factor) FOR DAMS ONLY!	n.a.	1-2	1-2	1-2	na	1	1	1	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2	1-2
BFBILE	100	100	100	50	40	100	90	90	100	100	100	100	100	100	60

The index is not applicable to lakes of SWB type L09 and L10, as well as all lakes or reservoirs that are used as a whole for aquaculture purposes and therefore are permanently stocked with fish, hence representing an artificial fish population (Data annex chapter 9.3). For L9 and L10, the data revealed a high variability and heterogeneity of the fish communities and fish abundance is highly varying seasonally, as the connection of these two lake types with the Black Sea is permanent. This situation does not allow developing a classification system for these two types. Due to the location between freshwater and marine environments, a higher sampling effort is needed to provide reliable data, as an assessment by a single sampling occasion is not possible.

4.3 Pressure – Response Relationship

4.3.1 Pressure Index calculation

To create a Pressure Index (PI), the Pressure Index as from 2016 intercalibration exercise (IC) was used and adapted (see Chapter 3.3.1). The pressure index (PI) includes the weighted sum of defined hydromorphological pressures, (assumed) toxic impact and Corine landcover. The selected parameters were chosen by evaluating their significance in the correlation with the biological response metrics.

The PI for Lakes is calculated as the sum of the weighted pressures as follows:

$PI = \text{migration Barriers} + \text{impoundment} + \text{temperature alteration} + \text{riparian vegetation alteration (seg)} * 2 + \text{habitat alteration (site)} * 2 + \text{toxicity} * 10 + \text{water level fluctuation} + \text{aquaculture} + \text{invasive species} + \text{fish introductions}$

4.3.2 Relationship between pressure index (PI) and nEQR

The pressure – response relationship with PI as independent variable and nEQR as dependent variable is shown in Figure 6. The calculated result is highly significant and explains 39% of the total variance (R^2 of 0.39 - which corresponds to a correlation coefficient of - 0.63). The regression model exceeds the recommended r value according to the CIS Guidance Documents on IC. The outcome of the regression model is shown in

Table 13.

Figure 6: Correlation between the pressure index and the nEQR based on the index BFBILE.

Table 13. Linear regression model Pressure Index PI vs nEQR calculated from BFBILE.

Linear regression model: Biotic Index nEQR ~ Pressure Index PI

```
Call:
lm(formula = nEQR ~ PI, data = data)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-0.57329 -0.17827  0.00465  0.19049  0.44049

Coefficients:
            Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  0.958102   0.094796  10.107 2.27e-13 ***
PI          -0.042757   0.007765  -5.506 1.49e-06 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 0.2609 on 47 degrees of freedom
Multiple R-squared:  0.3921,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.3792
F-statistic: 30.32 on 1 and 47 DF,  p-value: 1.493e-06
```

As the hierarchical structure of the data set implies, the boxplots of nEQR and PI indicate a slightly varying distribution among WB Types (Figure 7 & Figure 8). Furthermore, the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) is pointing on a minor group effect and therefore mixed effect models were created. The calculations were carried out in R with the package *lme4* (Bates *et al.* 2015; Bates *et al.* 2012). Due to the low sample size per SWB type, no random effects could be detected (Table 14).

Figure 7: Boxplot of nEQR by SWB type.

Figure 8: Boxplot of Pressure Index by SWB type.

Table 14. Linear mixed model with Pressure Index as fixed variable and SWB type as random factor.

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

Linear mixed model fit by REML ['lmerMod']

Formula: nEQR ~ PI + (1 | WBType)

Data: data

REML criterion at convergence: 18

Scaled residuals:

Min	1Q	Median	3Q	Max
-2.19762	-0.68337	0.01784	0.73021	1.68854

Random effects:

Groups	Name	Variance	Std.Dev.
WBType	(Intercept)	0.00000	0.0000
	Residual	0.06805	0.2609

Number of obs: 49, groups: WBType, 14

Fixed effects:

	Estimate	Std. Error	t value
(Intercept)	0.958102	0.094796	10.107
PI	-0.042757	0.007765	-5.506

Correlation of Fixed Effects:

(Intr)

PI -0.919

optimizer (nloptwrap) convergence code: 0 (OK)

boundary (singular) fit: see ?isSingular

The statistical analyses show a significant and strong response of fish communities on anthropogenic pressures (PI).

5 Reference conditions and class boundaries for the ecological status

5.1 Reference values

Due to the fact that most water bodies in Bulgaria are affected by various anthropogenic factors, it is difficult to establish reference conditions and define exact reference values for all parameters used in the TsBRI. Accordingly, the least-disturbed Bulgarian sites are characterized by near-reference conditions.

Reference values were derived from the combination of:

- Best available (= near-reference) sites: Index values preferably higher than 0.85 for the last sampling years;
- Historical data: species community, mainly presence/absence (partly dominance);
- Expert judgment, based on the ecological requirements of the species and the abiotic characteristics in the national river types and fish regions.

Type specific communities were determined for all national river types, which were intercalibrated, as well as all fish zones occurring in these types. The classification of fish species according to their dominance in different national types and fish regions follows the approach of Austria, Germany and Slovenia.

The reference TsBRI values for each river type / fish zone were derived as follow:

- the reference coenosis was defined. Taxa were classified as dominant, accompanying or rare species (see Data annex chapter 9.2);
- The relative proportion was converted to abundance under the following assumptions:
 - total abundance = 10,000 ind./ha;
 - relative proportion of dominant species = 75%;
 - relative proportion accompanying species = 20%;
 - relative proportion of rare species = 5%;
 - All species within each dominance class were evenly distributed, but finally evaluated by expert judgment depending on ecology.
- Biomass was roughly derived by assuming a mean weight per individual and fish;
- Age class was estimated as follows:
 - 1 = natural, all age classes present;
 - 2 = some age classes missing or only with a few specimens;
 - 3 = several age classes missing;
 - Under reference conditions, all taxa should have age class 1, but given a defined sampling method, rare species will hardly be caught in all size classes (e.g. predatory species). Hence, even under reference conditions, only dominant species should have age class 1, while accompanying species may have 1 or 2 and rare species 2 or 3.

The TsBRI reference values for each river type / fish zone as developed 2016 during the Intercalibration Project are listed in Table 15. Under the current assignment, reference fish communities were developed for the remaining river types R1, R3, R5, R9, R10, R11, R12, R13, R15

and R16 in ecoregion 12 & 7. The TsBRI reference values for each river type / fish zone in ecoregion 12 & 7 can be seen in Table 17.

Table 15. River types, fish zones and reference values for the TsBRI. For each type/zone, the number of dominant, subdominant (= accompanying) and rare species as well as the total species richness under reference conditions is given.

Ecoregion	12									7			
	DR							BS		WA	EA		
River type	R2	R2	R4	R4	R6	R7	R8	R2	R4	R4	R14	R14	R14
Fish zone	ER	MR	MR	HR	EP	EP	HR/EP	MR	MR	HR	MR	HR	HR
dominant	1	2	2	3	7	4	4	1	1	4	2	2	3
accompanying	1	3	4	4	16	5	4	4	4	2	2	4	5
rare	0	5	7	10	33	26	13	3	3	7	2	5	2
total	2	10	13	17	56	35	21	8	8	13	6	11	10
TsBRI reference value	59	69	65	79	–	78	74	70	72	82	80	64	80

Ecoregion 12 = Pontic province (Danube river basin), 7 = Eastern Balkan (Mediterranean catchment). Water sheds: DR = Danube River, BS = Black Sea, WA/EA = Western / Eastern Aegean. The Danube River itself (R6) is not covered by different modification of the method. ER = epirhithral, MR = metarhithral, HR = hyporhithral, EP = epipotamal.

5.2 Final list of reference (benchmark) sites

At the European level, all reference sites have to be qualified as minimally disturbed sites at the local scale, using a set of common variables describing the intensity of different types of pressures (water quality, hydro-morphological pressures, connectivity alteration...). These sites are mentioned as “undisturbed sites” or “non-disturbed sites” (NDS).

Undisturbed sites were defined using the criteria listed in

Table 16. No information was available for the criteria “water quality index”, “water quality alteration” and “fish farms / ponds”. However, the sites selected based on the other criteria are known by expert judgment not to be affected by these three criteria. The selected sites could thus be accepted as NDS. Non disturbed sites (NDS) are classified undisturbed (“yes”) or not (“no”) regarding to the common criteria listed below.

Table 16. Criteria used for undisturbed sites selection. Only sites characterized by no or low pressure intensity (depending of the considered pressure) are selected (red modalities).

Pressure type	Scale	Pressure intensity				Nb of modalities
Presence of downstream artificial barriers on the catchment scale	catchment	no	low	high		3
Artificial barriers upstream from the site	segment	no	low	medium	high	4
Artificial barriers downstream from the site	segment	no	low	medium	high	4
Impoundment	site	no	low	high		3
Hydropeaking	site	no	low	high		3
Water abstraction	site	no	low	medium	high	4
Colinear connected reservoir (fish farms, fish ponds ...)	segment	no	high			2
Upstream dams influence	site	no	low	high		3
Water temperature modification (excluding dam effect)	site	no	high			2
Channelisation / Cross section alteration (segment scale)	segment	no	low	medium	high	4
Riparian vegetation	site	no	low	medium	high	4
Local Habitat alteration	site	no	low	medium	high	4
Dykes (flood protection)	segment	no	low	medium	high	4
Toxic Risk. Priority substances list	segment	no	low	high		3
Water acidification	segment	no	low	high		3
National water quality index (segment scale)	segment	no	low	medium	high	4
Water quality alteration (local scale)	site	no	low	medium	high	4
Navigation	segment	no	high			2
Recreational use with high intensity (angling, boating,...)	site	no	high			2
impairment of indigenous species	segment	no	high			2
heavy predation	site	no	high			2
major effect on indigenous populations by stocking activities	segment	no	high			2

The National reference sites (NRS) are the sites classified as reference sites by Bulgaria regarding to the national criteria (EQR for TsBRI ≥ 0.85). Based on these criteria, 38 sites, sampled in 2020 could be identified and were considered as candidate reference sites. It must be stressed that the selection aims at developing the classification system but does not necessarily mean that all these sites truly represent reference conditions.

The Intercalibration reference sites correspond to all sites, which are both classified as non-disturbed (NDS = “yes”) and as a national reference site (NRS = “yes”) as well as Exceptional disturbed sites accepted as reference sites (ERS = “yes”). The Exceptional reference sites (ERS) are the sites classified as a reference sit, while it is considered as a disturbed site (a good justification is given).

5.3 Class boundaries

Neither any discontinuity in the relationship between pressure and the impact nor a paired metric analysis (both approaches according to Guidance Document No. 14) was helpful to set the boundaries for the status classes. Following Step 8 of the Boundary Setting Protocol (CIS Guidance Document No. 14 (EC 2011), page 65), the continuum of impact was divided into equal width classes.

In a first step, the H/G boundary was defined as the 25th percentile of the EQR values of the reference sites (IRS), which is 0.86. Then, the remaining gradient was divided to get equal distance class boundaries. The EQR boundaries are:

H/G boundary 0.86

G/M boundary 0.65

M/P boundary 0.43

P/B boundary 0.22

Table 17 summarises the type-specific TsBRI values of the different water bodies.

Table 17. Class boundaries: Type-specific values for the fish index TsBRI in Bulgarian rivers.

	R1 ER	R2 ER	R2 MR	R2 BS	R3 ER	R3a MR WA	R3b HR EA	R5 MR	R5a HR WA	R5b HR EA	R7 EP	R8 HR_EP	R9 HR	R10 HR	R10 EP	R11 L	R11 S	R12 EP	R12 MP	R13 EA	R13 WA	R14a WA MR	R14b EA MR	R14b EA HR	R14c EA HR	R15 EA.WA	R15 BS	R15 DR	R16
Reference	72	59	69	70	75	78	78	75	89	90	78	74	30	87	79	85	57	93	98	40	60	80	64	80	37	22	50	57	85
H/G	62	51	59	60	65	67	67	65	77	77	67	64	26	75	68	73	49	80	84	34	52	69	55	69	32	19	43	49	73
G/M	47	38	45	46	49	51	51	49	58	59	51	48	20	57	51	55	37	60	64	26	39	52	42	52	24	14	33	37	55
M/P	31	25	30	30	32	34	34	32	38	39	34	32	13	37	34	37	25	40	42	17	26	34	28	34	16	9	22	25	37
P/B	16	13	15	15	17	17	17	17	20	20	17	16	7	19	17	19	13	20	22	9	13	18	14	18	8	5	11	13	19
min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 18. Class boundaries: Type-specific values for the fish Index BFBILE in Bulgarian lakes.

	L01	L02	L03	L04A	L04B	L06	L07	L08	L11	L12	L13	L14	L15	L16	L17
Reference	100	100	100	50	40	100	90	90	100	100	100	100	100	100	60
H/G	80	86	68	40	32	70	72	67	84	86	74	74	86	74	44
G/M	60	65	48	30	24	50	54	49	64	65	54	54	65	54	32
M/P	40	45	28	20	16	30	36	31	44	45	34	34	45	34	20
P/B	20	25	8	10	8	10	18	13	24	25	14	14	25	14	8
min	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

6 Heavily modified water bodies and ecological potential

6.1 RIVERS

Annex 1 of the Final Report is a general document on ecological potential (thereafter named GD-EP) and describes the principle of ecological potential (EP) classification as defined in the CIS Guidance No 37. Two routes are possible to define the maximum and good ecological potential (MEP, GEP): the reference approach (as already described in CIS Guidance No 4) and the mitigation measures or Prague approach. The first requires information on the BQE to define boundaries for biological metrics at MEP and/or GEP, the latter focusses on possible measures, which influence the hydromorphological and physical-chemical conditions and, hence, the biological communities.

The GD-EP covers the first steps of EP definition:

- Step A. Identification of closest comparable water category
- Step B. Identify mitigation measures
 - Step B1. Identify mitigation measures relevant to each of the hydromorphological alterations and ecologically effective in the physical context of the water body
 - Step B2. Exclude mitigation measures with significant adverse effect on use or wider environment
 - Step B3. Select most ecologically beneficial (combination of) measures taking into account need to ensure best approximation to ecological continuum
- Step C. Derivation of hydromorphological conditions for MEP
- Step D. Derivation of physico-chemical conditions for MEP, taking into account the closest comparable water body type

In this Annex, we evaluate the possibility to use fish for MEP/GEP definition. We will use the outcome of the GD-EP and concentrate on the remaining steps as defined in CIS Guidance No 37:

- Step E. Derivation of BQE conditions for MEP
- Step F. Derivation of BQE conditions for GEP
- Step G. Derivation of supporting quality element conditions for GEP
- Step H. Identification of mitigation measures for GEP

While step G and H can only be roughly covered from an ichthyological point of view, the main task is to find a way of defining the BQE conditions under MEP (Step E) and GEP (Step F).

6.1.1 River types where the environmental objectives for ES can be met in HMWB

River types R1, R2, R6 and R15

As some river types do not include any HMWB, this chapter will cover only the river types R3–R5 and R7–R14. Like for the other BQE, no BQE specific information or class boundaries can be defined to assess the EP of R1, R2 and R15. The river Danube R6 is outside the scope of this project.

River types R5 and R7

Like for benthic invertebrates, most SWB belonging to the river types R5 and R7 do not show a significant impact on structures relevant for fish and seem also not significantly affected by water abstraction. They show dynamics; habitat structures and in-channel diversity seem to be intact and only slightly to moderately altered. Based on screening on Google Earth, the designation of these SWB as heavily modified should be re-evaluated. Therefore, there is little reason to assume that it should not be possible for the BQE fish to reach good ecological status (GES). Not surprisingly and similar to the outcome of the MZB classification, several sites sampled in 2020 belonging to these types, turned out to be in good or even high ecological status. Therefore, we recommend keeping the boundaries and BI classes for EP in these two river types as defined for ES and not set lower environmental objectives, at least for the river sections of larger rivers with dynamics within the channel. *For smaller rivers belonging to R5, lower environmental objectives are justified (see below).*

River type R10

Also the three HMWB belonging to R10 do not seem significantly altered in the structures and habitat characteristics relevant for the BQE fish in spite of reduced lateral connectivity. Taking into account mitigation measures as described in chapter 4.7.2 of the GD-EP, good or even high ecological status can be possible for the HMWB of R10. The result of the sampling in 2020 at two R10 sites revealed good status in one case, and moderate status in the other (exactly like for MZB).

River type R14

Only 2 of 50 SWB belonging to this type are heavily modified: Alamovska reka (BG3AR400R018; *see below*) and Kalamitsa river (BG3MA100R002). The latter includes a small reservoir, which probably abstracts water and thus affects the downstream river stretch until the Turkish border. No data on the fish community are available from this SWB, but the anthropogenic impacts seem severe enough to significantly alter the fish communities. However, water abstraction is usually not considered as a reason for not reaching GES. Unless it can be proved that providing ecological flow to the Kalamitsa river has a significant adverse effect on the use, GES should be possible in this case. Therefore, we recommend keeping the boundaries and BI classes for EP as defined for ES and not set lower environmental objectives.

6.1.2 River types where lower environmental objectives for EP than for ES are justified

River type R9

Among 12 SWB belonging to the river type R9 (Danube Dobrudzha rivers), only one is considered as heavily modified (BG1DJ900R1011, Suha reka). It includes one larger reservoir in the middle section, which abstracts a significant proportion of discharge within a naturally dry and karstic region. Hence,

water flow is often very limited. For the BQE benthic invertebrates it was concluded that even when implementing some of the mitigation measures described in the GD-EP, a significant deviation from GES can still be expected. The same should be true for the BQE fish. Nevertheless, the assessment revealed good status. Unless more data are available, we recommend to follow the approach suggested for benthic invertebrates and accept lower boundaries for GEP than for GES. As the only available sampling suggests good status, the mitigation measures approach should be followed to define SWB-specific measures.

River type R12

The river type R12 includes sections of the rivers Maritsa and Tundzha. Only 1 of 10 SWB is heavily modified (a section of Maritsa between approximately Pazardzhik and Plovdiv). In-channel diversity and riparian structure seem to be largely intact, although the river like many others has lost its inundation area in the larger floodplain. While water abstraction seems not to critically affect the benthic community (see Annex 4 “Benthic Invertebrates” of the Final Report), there could be an impact on fish due to the loss of lateral connectivity. Therefore, lower environmental objectives than required to achieve ES seem justified.

River type R14

As stated above, only 2 of 50 SWB belonging to this type are heavily modified. Alamovska reka (BG3AR400R018) flows from Alamovska reservoir until the town Zlatograd. It is partly channelised for flood protection and may additionally be impacted by water abstraction. Immediately before the confluence with the Varbitsa river, within the town Zlatograd, the Alamovska river flows underground. Even with some improvement when considering the mitigation measures described in the GD-EP, a significant deviation from GES is expected. Lower boundaries are thus justified.

River types, R3, R4, R8, R11, R13

Most of these river flow through agricultural areas and are channelized. Dynamics and habitat diversity are reduced. In the GD-EP, several mitigations measures were identified, which would improve conditions for fish as well as for other BQE. The results from the campaign 2020 reveal that some of the HMWB sites are in good or even high ecological status, which demonstrates that it is doubtful whether uniform type-specific methods to assess the EP of heavily modified rivers are reasonable. Like for the BQE benthic invertebrates, a site-specific evaluation is recommended.

6.1.3 Theoretical options to set boundaries for EP in the reference approach

The options for EP boundary setting are generally described in Annex 4 “Benthic Invertebrates” of the Final Report. Similar to the situation for this BQE, we recommend also for the BQE fish a simple and pragmatic approach:

- For types or single HMWB, where achieving GES is possible, the EP as assessed by the BQE fish should be defined in the same way as the ES.
- For types or single HMWB, where achieving GES is not possible, the boundaries of the EP classes for the BI shall be defined 1 step lower as for ES.

A list of all HMWB sampled in 2020 with the proposed classification results for the ecological potential following the reference approach as described above is included in the Access Project Database.

6.1.4 Mitigation measures or Prague approach

If the **mitigation measures or Prague approach** – or a combination of reference and mitigation measures approach – shall be followed, the measures selected chapter 4 of the DG-EP are used as a starting point. Tab. 23 of the DG-EP lists the most ecologically beneficial mitigation measures in rivers. For fish and in the types discussed above, the following set of mitigation measures is considered as most relevant and necessary to achieve the **maximum ecological potential**:

- Fish migration aids!
- Ecological flow!
- Riparian habitat enhancement
- Improvement of in-channel diversity
- Increase habitat diversity (depth, width)
- Floodplains / off-channel / lateral connect.
- Channel enhancement
- Vegetation enhancement / rehabilitation
- Reduction of negative effects of impoundment
- Rehabilitation of phys-chem alteration
- Intertidal habitat restoration

Under **good ecological potential**, we propose the following set of mitigation measures:

- Fish migration aids!
- Ecological flow!
- Riparian habitat enhancement (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Improvement of in-channel diversity (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Increase habitat diversity (depth, width) (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Reduction of negative effects of impoundment
- Rehabilitation of phys-chem alteration

6.2 LAKES

Similar to the situation on benthic invertebrates, it is neither possible to describe the fish community under the mitigation measures defined in the GD-EP (→ MEP) nor when considering slight deviations (→ GEP). Concluding, the **reference approach cannot be recommended** for the classification of the EP based on the BQE fish in lakes. Even the pragmatic approach of defining EP as 1 class below ES (e.g., moderate status = GEP), as proposed for rivers, is not justified.

In the **mitigation measures or Prague approach**, GEP is defined by removing measures only leading to slight changes in the biological conditions. Tab. 22 of the GD-EP lists the most ecologically beneficial mitigation measures in lakes. For fish, the following set of mitigation measures is considered as most relevant and necessary to achieve the **maximum ecological potential**:

- Enhancement of shore/shallow habitats (especially in the littoral zone)
- Creation of secondary habitats
- Where possible, management of lake level by reducing the water level fluctuations and by limiting the rate of lowering the water level (to allow large and mobile animals following the water)
- Management of lake use / designation of protected areas
- Ecologically optimised fisheries!
- Fish migration aids / connectivity (tributaries, upstream)
- Mitigation of physical-chemical conditions
- Beneficial use of dredged material

Under **good ecological potential**, we propose the following set of mitigation measures:

- Enhancement of shore/shallow habitats (especially in the littoral zone)
- Creation of secondary habitats (at smaller scale than under MEP)
- Where possible, management of lake level by limiting the rate of lowering the water level
- Management of lake use / designation of protected areas
- Ecologically optimised fisheries!
- Fish migration aids / connectivity (tributaries, upstream)
- Mitigation of physical-chemical conditions

7 Conclusion

The following table gives an overview of the classification of ecological status of river and lakes/reservoirs. It does not consider different approaches to define the EP for HMWB (see Access Project Database).

Table 19. Results of the ecological assessment of rivers and lakes sampled in 2020.

	High	Good	Moderate	Poor	Bad
Rivers	31	28	18	15	17
Lakes	13	7	7	11	11

Rivers

The development/validation of the classification system for the assessment of the ecological status of the various Bulgarian river and lake types, that have not yet been included within the intercalibration exercise, is a challenging task, but field work, data acquisition and statistical analyses for the BQE fish have shown that the Bulgarian fish index for rivers (TsBRI) is a well-working and useful index and responds significantly to pressures. Available data on fish and relevant pressures in various river types were evaluated and reference conditions and reference values were defined. A total of 31 potential National reference sites (NRS) in rivers, regarding to the national criteria (EQR for TsBRI ≥ 0.85), could be identified and were considered as candidate reference sites. Class boundaries for all river types are set and sampling sites can be evaluated according to these boundaries.

Lakes

The definition and description of type-specific fish communities for the different lake/reservoir types were followed by the adaptation of the, already intercalibrated BFBI-L5 Index, and the development of the new Bulgarian Fish Based Index for Assessing the Ecological Quality of Lentic Ecosystems (BFBILE) for new lake/reservoir types. The calculation of the BFBILE Index for lake/reservoir sampled in 2020 and the statistical analyses to identify the relationship between pressures and BFBILE Index response in lake/reservoir has been successfully completed. The pressure response relationship of the newly developed BFBILE showed strong and significant relationship between fish communities and anthropogenic pressures. A total of 13 potential National reference sites (NRS) in lakes/reservoirs, regarding to the national criteria (EQR for BFBILE ≥ 0.85), could be identified and were considered as candidate reference sites. Class boundaries for all lake types are set and sampling sites can be evaluated according to these boundaries. However, no classification method could be developed for the poly- and hyperhaline lake types L9 and L10, due to high variability and heterogeneity. For these two lake types, a higher sampling effort is needed to provide reliable data. Besides, no fish classification is feasible in all lakes or reservoirs that are used as a whole for aquaculture purposes and therefore are permanently stocked with fish, hence representing an artificial fish population.

HMWB and Ecological potential

Similar to the situation on the BQE benthic invertebrates, the boundaries for EP can be the same as for ES, since GES seems achievable without significant adverse effects on the use. This results that the designation of some HMWB should be reconsidered and revised. For some types, lower boundaries are justified. At present, the pragmatic approach to accept one class below ES as the assessment for EP seems most feasible. For lakes as well as for selected river monitoring sites, however, the reference approach should not be applied. We rather recommend pursuing the mitigation measures approach until more data and a deeper understanding of ecological functioning is available.

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9 Data Annex

9.1 Surface waterbody types

WB_type	Description	Ecoregion	Geology class	Altitude	Catchment	Distance from source	Slope	Valley shape	Substrate	Salinity
R01	High mountain (Alpine) rivers	12-1; 7	mixed	>1800	<100	<15	>10%	V, narrow U	bedrock, rocks, boulders	<0.5‰
R02	Mountainous rivers (Uplands)	12-1; 2	mixed	mountainous	<100	<40	(2) 4-10%	V, narrow U	boulders, cobbles	<0.5‰
R03	Mountainous rivers (Uplands)	7	mixed	>(600)800	<150 (500)	<80	(2) 4-10%	V, narrow U	boulders, cobbles	<0.5‰
R04	Semimountainous rivers (gravel rivers)	12-1; 2	mixed	variable	<1300	>>	<2%	U	fine - coarse gravel	<0.5‰
R05	Semimountainous rivers (gravel rivers)	7	mixed	variable	<1300	>>	<2%	U	fine - coarse gravel	<0.5‰
R06	Lower Danube	12-1	mixed	<30	>800 000	>1500	<0.1%	very broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R07	Large Danube tributaries	12-1	mixed	<80	>2500	>70	<0.5%	broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R08	medium and small Danube rivers	12-1	mixed	<100	<1300	variable	<0.5%	broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R09	Losing karst rivers Dobrudja area	12-1	calcareous	<300	<4000	variable	variable		variable	<0.5‰
R10	Large Black Sea rivers	12-2	mixed	<90	>1000	>50	<0.5%	broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R11	Small and medium Black Sea rivers	12-2	mixed	<70	<900	variable	<0.5%	broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R12	Large floodplain rivers	7	mixed	<150 (200)	<7000	variable	<1%	broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R13	Small and medium floodplain rivers	7	mixed	<150 (350)	<1300	variable	<1%	broad	clay - sand	<0.5‰
R14	Sub-Mediterranean (temporary)	7	mixed	<500 (650)	<1100	variable	variable	variable	variable	<0.5‰
R15	Karst springs	12; 7	calcareous	variable	<10	<5	-	-	variable	<0.5‰
R16	Black Sea river firths	12-2	mixed; siliceous	<5 (12)	variable	>15	very gentle	broad	clay - sand	oligohaline

9.2 Reference list of fish coenoses by ecoregion, basin, river type and biocoenotic region.

Abbreviations see at the end of the table

Scientific name	reference communities																																							
	ER	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7			
	Shed	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	DR	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA	WA		
	Type	R2	R2	R4	R6	R7	R8	R9	R15	R2	R4	R4	R10	R10	R11	R11	R15	R16	R1	R3	R3a	R5	R5a	R13	R15	R14a	R1	R3	R3b	R5	R5b	R12	R12	R13	R15	R14b	R14b	R14c		
Zone	ER	MR	MR	HR	EP	EP	HR/EP	HR	Spring	MR	MR	HR	HR	EP	Large	Small	Spring	Trans	ER	ER	MR	MR	HR	EP	Spring	MR	ER	ER	HR	MR	HR	EP	IMP	EP	Spring	MR	HR	HR		
	2DRR2	DRR2	DRR4	DRR4	DRR6	DRR7	DRR8	DRR9	DRR15	DRR2	DRR4	DRR4	DRR10	DRR10	DRR11	DRR11	DRR15	DRR16	DRR1	DRR3	DRR3a	DRR5	DRR5a	DRR13	DRR15	DRR14a	DRR1	DRR3	DRR3b	DRR5	DRR5b	DRR12	DRR12	DRR13	DRR15	DRR14b	DRR14b	DRR14c		
Abramis ballerus					++	+																																		
Abramis brama					+++	+	+																																	
Abramis sapa					+++																																			
Abramis sp.						+																																		
Acipenser ruthenus						+																																		
Acipenser stellatus						+																																		
Acipenser gueldenstaedtii						+																																		
Acipenser nudiventris						+																																		
Acipenser sp.						+																																		
Alburnoides sp.		++	++	+++		+	++			++	++	+++	+								+		+	+		+	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX
Alburnus alburnus					++	+++	+++	+++					+	+	+																							++	++	
Alburnus (Alburnus) sp.					++	+++	+++	+++																														++	++	
Alburnus (Chalcalburnus) sp.						+							+	+	+					+																				
Alosa immaculata						+																																		
Alosa tanaica						+																																		
Alosa sp.						+																																		
Ameiurus melas	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Anguilla anguilla	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Aspius aspius					++	+																																		
Atherina sp.																																								
Barbus barbus					++	++	+++	++																																
Barbus bergi										++	++	+++	+++	++																										
Barbus cyclolepis																						+++	+++	++	++	+++		+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	
Barbus petenyi		+++	+++	+++		++	+++	+++																																
Benthophiloides braueri																																								
Benthophilus stellatus						+																																		
Blicca bjoerkna					+++	+	+																																	
Carassius carassius						+																																		
Carassius gibelio	EX	EX	EX	EX	+++	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Chondrostoma nasus					+	+	++	+													EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Chondrostoma vardarense																						+																+	+	
Chondrostoma sp.						+	+	++	+																														+	+
Cobitis elongata																																								
Cobitis elongatoides		+	+	+	++	++	++					+	+	+																										
Cobitis pontica													+	+	++	+	+	+																						
Cobitis strumicae		+	+	+	++	++	++																					++	++	+++	+++	+		+++	++	+				
Cobitis sp.		+	+	+	++	++	++					+	+	++	+	+	+										++	++	+++	+++	+		+++	++	+					
Coregonus sp.	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Cottus gobio	++	+	+																																					
Ctenopharyngodon idella	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Cyprinus carpio						++																																		
Engraulis encrasicolus																																								
Esox lucius					+	+	+	++	+	+																														
Eudontomyzon mariae																																								
Eudontomyzon sp.																																								
Gambusia sp.	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	EX	
Gasterosteus aculeatus						+																																		

9.3 Reference list of fish coenoses by lake type

	L01	L02	L03	L04	L05	L05a	L06	L11	L11a	L11b	L11c	L12	L13	L14	L15	L16	L17	L07	L08	L09	L10
Ecoregion					12	7	7		12	7	7	12	7	12	7	12	7	12	12	12	12
Surface area km²	<10	<10	0.1-21	<5	<5	<5	<5	>10	>10	>10	>10	<10	<10	>5	>5	<5	<5				
Altitude	>200	200-800	800-2000	200-800	<200	<200	<500		200-800	200-400	>1000	200-800	200-800	<200	<200	<200	<200	<200	<200	<200	<200
Category									Res.	Res.	Res.	Res.	Res.	Res.	Res.	Res.	Res.	nat	nat	nat	nat
Reference trophic state (as TP conc. µg/L)	3	4	4	6	30	30	30		8	8	4	8	8	12	12	15	15	20	20	20	20
Salinity	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	0‰	>	>	>10‰	>20‰
Phoxinus sp.	++																				
Salmo trutta	+										+										
Alburnus alburnus		+++					+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++				
Carassius gibelio		++		X			++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++	++			+	
Perca fluviatilis		++	++	X			+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++		
Rutilus rutilus		++	++	X			+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	+++	++		
Squalius sp./orpheus		+	+				+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+				
Esox lucius		+	+	+			+	+	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+	+			
Scardinius erythrophthalmus							+						+	+	+			+	+		
Sander lucioperca		+	+					+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+		
Vimba sp.							+	+	+	+			+	+	+	+					
Cyprinus carpio		+	+	+			+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+		
Neogobius melanostomus																		+++		++	
Neogobius gymnotrachelus																		+			
Engraulis encrasicolus																				+	
Liza saliens																				+	
Mugil cephalus																				+	
Syngnathus abaster																				+	+
Proterorhinus marmoratus																				+	
Atherina sp.																				+	+
Gasterosteus aculeatus																				+	+
Knipowitschia sp.																		+	+		+++
Silurus glanis		+					+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+				
Rhodeus amarus		+		+			++	+	+	+		+	+	+	+	+	+	++	+		

9.4 RESERVOIRS TOTALLY USED FOR AQUACULTURE, WHERE NO CLASSIFICATION BASED ON THE BQE FISH IS POSSIBLE

SiteCode	WBType	SiteName	Comment
BG3AR00086MS0290	L03	Smolianski Lakes (Trevisto Lake)	The fish fauna of all tectonic Smolian Lakes is entirely artificial
BG2KA47379MS488	L04	Skala 1 Reservoir	The index is not applicable to lakes /dams, which are totally used for aquaculture (permanent stockings).
BG2KA00233MS037	L12	Eleshnitsa Reservoir	
BG2KA08471MS261	L12	Fisek Reservoir	
BG1YN04471MS031	L12	Krapets Reservoir	
BG4ST06963MS945	L13	Dolna Dikanya Reservoir	
BG1VT00325MS031	L14	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	
BG3MA00225MS0120	L15	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	
BG3MA00324MS1239	L15	Garvanovo Reservoir	
BG2SE08331MS028	L16	Aheloy Reservoir	
BG1WO00814MS071	L16	Rasovo Reservoir	
BG1WO00814MS071	L16	Rasovo Reservoir	
BG2SE98935MS263	L16	Troyanovo	
BG3MA03929MS0371	L17	Byalo Pole Reservoir	
BG3MA00347MS0280	L17	General Nikolaevo Reservoir-1	
BG3MA03929MS0371	L17	Sushitsa Reservoir	
BG3MA00347MS0280	L17	Mechka Reservoir	

9.5 CLASSIFICATION RESULTS FOR RIVERS

SiteCode	SiteName	WBType	PI	Ref	TsBRI	EQR	nEQR
BG4ST06582MS405	Iliina River, before the estuary of Rilska River	R01	3.07	72	68	0.94	0.91
BG4ST65891MS402	Rilska River, before Rila Monastery	R01	1.07	72	68	0.94	0.91
BG4ST65149MS401	Sandanska Bistritsa River, below Popina Luka	R01	4.00	72	70	0.97	0.96
BG4ME47389MS403	Retidzhe River, before HPP 1	R01	1.00	72	72	1.00	1.00
BG4ST06569MS401	Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River - "Kartalska polyana" Meadow	R01	2.00	72	68	0.94	0.91
BG4ST06569MS402	Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River, after Bodrost area, before Slavova River	R01	3.00	72	68	0.94	0.91
BG4ST00632MS601	Mochura River, Stefanov peak	R01	3.00	72	70	0.97	0.96
BG3MA00094MS1462	Yadenitsa River - after Yundola	R03	6.15	75	68	0.91	0.87
BG4ME47521MS401	Bezbozhka River, before estuary, bridge on the road for Gotse Delchev	R03	3.01	75	61	0.81	0.75

SiteCode	SiteName	WBType	PI	Ref	TsBRI	EQR	nEQR
BG3MA00995MS1571	Maritsa River before the town of Dolna Banya	R03	10.54	75	67	0.89	0.84
BG3MA00997MS1580	Maritsa River near the village of Raduil	R03	6.54	75	61	0.81	0.75
BG3MA05295MS0630	Chepelarska River, after Chepelare	R03	16.07	75	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ST06669MS401	Otovitsa River, after Otovitsa Hut	R03	4.00	75	70	0.93	0.90
BG4ST65341MS401	Vlahinska River, before Sinanishka River inflow near Vlahi village	R03	2.08	75	68	0.91	0.87
BG4ST06541MS403	Gradevska River, before the estuary, t. Simitli	R03	11.69	82	59	0.72	0.67
BG3AR00773MS0270	Arda River, Vehtino village	R03	2.52	78	72	0.92	0.89
BG3AR00951MS0385	Arda River before the town of Rudozem	R03	8.69	78	85	1.09	1.00
BG3AR00721MS0221	Davidkovska River - estuary, bridge after Lyubino village	R03	5.13	78	29	0.37	0.34
BG3MA00523MS0594	Chepelarska River, after Bachkovo village, between the two tunnels	R03	7.15	78	26	0.33	0.30
BG3MA00094MS1461	Yadenitsa River - Belovo	R03	16.15	78	19	0.24	0.22
BG3TU00723MS0171	Asenovska River - before Sliven, after plashes	R03	21.54	78	17	0.22	0.20
BG4ME00478MS170	Zlataritsa River, before estuary	R03	25.22	78	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ME04569MS401	Nevrokopska River, before Gotse Delchev	R03	37.53	78	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ME04792MS401	Ruzhdavitsa River near Dobrinishte	R05	6.84	60	47	0.78	0.72
BG4ST65333MS403	Struma River before inflow of Belishka River (Shashka)	R05	14.11	75	63	0.84	0.78
BG4ME00481MS140	Iztok River, before inflowing in Mesta River	R05	4.61	75	34	0.45	0.42
BG3AR00159MS0040	Arda River, after Madzharovo - after the big turn	R05	6.10	90	34	0.38	0.35
BG3MA00861MS1172	Bunovshitsa River, after Smolska River inflow, before estuary	R05	11.53	90	19	0.21	0.19
BG3MA00471MS0490	Stryama River, Banya village	R05	10.93	90	30	0.33	0.30
BG3MA00811MS1070	Topolnitsa River - Pazardzhik, the bridge for Boshulia village, before estuary	R05	29.29	90	26	0.29	0.27
BG3MA00853MS1170	Topolnitsa River, before "Topolnitsa" Reservoir - near Poibrene village	R05	33.82	90	15	0.17	0.15
BG3MA04991MS0553	Stryama River, before Slatina village	R05	12.93	90	34	0.38	0.35
BG3TU00937MS0290	Tundzha River, Yagoda village, bridge on road Stara Zagora-Kazanlak	R05	24.35	90	79	0.88	0.83
BG1RL09391MS100	Beli Lom River, after Razgrad	R07	34.86	78	0	0.00	0.00
BG1VT00011MS010	Vit River, after Gulyantsi	R07	24.02	78	49	0.63	0.58
BG1YN00059MS130	Yantra River, near Draganovo village - after inflow of Lefedzha River	R07	16.33	78	60	0.77	0.71
BG1YN00061MS140	Lefedzha River, Briagovitsa village - before inflow into Yantra River	R07	12.37	78	67	0.86	0.80
BG1OG02431MS023	Ribene River, after Lesura village	R08	13.37	74	69	0.93	0.90
BG1OS00611MS040	Shavarna River, before inflow into Osam River	R08	21.51	74	51	0.69	0.64
BG1RL00231MS050	Cherni Lom River, before inflow with Banski Lom River near Ostritsa village	R08	28.09	74	47	0.64	0.59
BG1WO01621MS1100	Nechenska Bara River, before inflow into Lom River, bridge between Brusartsi and Kriva Bara village	R08	7.27	74	40	0.54	0.50

SiteCode	SiteName	WBType	PI	Ref	TsBRI	EQR	nEQR
BG1DJ99499MS070	r. Suha at v. Novo Botevo	R09	27.18	30	25	0.83	0.77
BG1DJ00096MS1040	r. Senkyovitsa at v. Golyama voda	R09	18.15	30	27	0.90	0.86
BG1DJ00043MS020	r. Tsaratsar downstream confluence of r. Voyka at v. Malak Porovets	R09	14.95	30	27	0.90	0.86
BG2KA00043MS301	Kamchiya River - Tsonevo village - Velichkovo village, after Luda Kamchiya River	R10	17.32	100	70	0.70	0.65
BG2KA900R1020	Kamchiya River, after Ticha Reservoir near V. Preslav	R10	21.06	100	42	0.42	0.39
BG2KA09153MS208	Kamchiya River – before V.Preslav	R10	23.31	100	67	0.67	0.62
BG2KA47522MS452	Kamchiya River - between Radko Dimitriev village and Salamanovo village	R10	22.33	100	57	0.57	0.53
BG2KA00513MS006	G. Kamchiya River - after Dalgopol	R10	21.13	100	59	0.59	0.55
BG2VE08179MS419	Veleka River - Brodlilovo village	R10	7.28	87	64	0.74	0.69
BG2KA04173MS233	Kamchiya River - Venelin village	R10	15.54	100	64	0.64	0.59
BG2KA41913MS302	Kamchiya River - Dabravino village	R10	13.54	100	73	0.73	0.68
BG2KA00119MS001	Kamchiya River - "Poda" area	R10	7.54	100	66	0.66	0.61
BG2KA00195MS002	Kamchiya River - Grozdiovo village	R10	10.32	100	74	0.74	0.69
BG2RE00219MS255	r. Silistar - upstream delta, bridge on the Rezovo - Sinemorets road	R11	0.00	57	56	0.98	0.97
BG2DO00831MS001	r. Batova - delta	R11	7.50	57	57	1.00	1.00
BG2IU76411MS410	r. Karaagach - v. Fazanovo	R11	1.33	77	81	1.05	1.00
BG2IU00291MS003	r. Ropotamo - v. Veselie downstream r. Mehmechkyoska	R11	4.96	85	81	0.95	0.93
BG2MA00221MS249	r. Izvorska - upstream delta between Dimchevo and Tvarditsa	R11	14.96	85	48	0.56	0.52
BG2SE09613MS015	r. Aytoska - downstream the city of Kameno	R11	24.09	85	25	0.29	0.27
BG2SE400R006RP08	r. Dvoynitsa, before the village of Popovich	R11	12.72	85	59	0.69	0.64
BG2PR00511MS005	r. Provadiyska - downstream the city of Provadia/after Provadsol	R11	48.57	77	15	0.19	0.17
BG2PR02517MS278	r. Provadiyska - upstream the city of Provadia	R11	22.39	77	30	0.39	0.36
BG2MA00713MS004	r. Sredetska - downstream the city of Sredets, Avramov bridge	R11	13.20	85	60	0.71	0.66
BG2MA66131MS364	r. Rusokastrenska - v. Trastikovo	R11	25.40	85	17	0.20	0.18
BG2PR00061MS020	r. Kriva – v. Enevo, delta	R11	27.34	85	0	0.00	0.00
BG2PR00071MS007	r. Provadiyska – downstream the city of Kaspichan	R11	43.95	85	0	0.00	0.00
BG2SE59639MS355	r. Aytoska downstream the city of Aitos	R11	43.25	85	0	0.00	0.00
BG2IU200R005RP14	Ropotamo River in MR "Veliov Vir"	R11	1.01	77	60	0.78	0.72
BG3MA00371MS0320	Maritsa River, Parvomay	R12	11.95	93	50	0.54	0.50
BG3TU00719MS0160	Tundzha River, Samuilovo village	R12	15.12	93	62	0.67	0.62
BG3MA00711MS0848	Maritsa River, before Vacha River	R12	13.61	93	39	0.42	0.39
BG3MA00055MS0670	Maritsa River, Plovdiv, walkways	R12	24.58	93	67	0.72	0.67
BG3MA00719MS0850	Maritsa River, Stamboliyski	R12	18.61	93	41	0.44	0.41

SiteCode	SiteName	WBType	PI	Ref	TsBRI	EQR	nEQR
BG3MA00739MS0910	Maritsa River Ognyanovo village	R12	17.61	93	28	0.30	0.28
BG3MA00731MS0902	Maritsa River, Govedare village	R12	20.61	93	43	0.46	0.43
BG3MA00077MS1060	Maritsa River - Pazardzhik	R12	23.61	93	42	0.45	0.42
BG3MA01191MS0010	Maritsa River, Svilengrad	R12	16.16	98	67	0.68	0.63
BG3MA00317MS4229	Maritsa River, Brod village	R12	13.35	98	77	0.79	0.73
BG3MA00017MS0020	Maritsa River, after Harmanli	R12	10.16	98	48	0.49	0.45
BG3TU00013MS0010	Tundzha River, Srem village	R12	5.30	98	60	0.61	0.56
BG3TU00539MS0061	Tundzha River, Elhovo	R12	15.10	98	55	0.56	0.52
BG3MA00041MS0400	r. Stryama, s. Manole	R13	12.58	40	37	0.93	0.90
BG3MA00421MS0403	Stryama River - Razhevo Konare village	R13	11.93	40	40	1.00	1.00
BG3MA00581MS0696	Potoka River - estuary, 9-th km of Plovdiv to Pazardzhik	R13	20.91	40	17	0.43	0.40
BG4ME00044MS403	Matnitsa River below Petrelik village	R13	6.47	60	49	0.82	0.76
BG4ST06961MS380	Arkata River, before inflow into Struma River	R13	34.42	60	40	0.67	0.62
BG3TU00665MS0126	Sigmen River - before Sigmen village	R13	9.00	40	0	0.00	0.00
BG3MA00229MS0132	Ovcharitsa River - Prohorovo village -ford of black road before the village	R13	22.18	40	0	0.00	0.00
BG3MA00213MS0090	Sazliyka River - before estuary; bridge for Svirkovo village and Troyan village	R13	17.97	36	22	0.61	0.56
BG3MA00318MS0232	Merichlerska River after Merichleri, bridge for Dlagnevo village	R13	28.96	40	0	0.00	0.00
BG3AR00161MS0043	Kulidjinska, at the end of the WB 800 m from delta in Ivailovgrad Dam "€" bridge in v. Bryagovets	R14	5.21	37	27	0.73	0.68
BG3TU00741MS0001	Fishera River - 500 m upstream Turkey border	R14	1.79	37	26	0.70	0.65
BG3AR00067MS0208	Borovitsa, about 200-250 m above the Borovitsa Reservoir	R14	3.00	37	24	0.65	0.60
BG3AR00661MS0206	Chataldjevitsa, delta under the wall of Borovitsa Dam	R14	8.31	37	22	0.59	0.55
BG3AR02949MS1059	Kodja dere, v. Malko Kamenyane	R14	3.23	37	26	0.70	0.65
BG3MA0B112MSB002	Luda reka - before confluence in Byala river	R14	1.77	37	34	0.92	0.89
BG3TU00552MS0080	Dereorman, Delta, bridge on the Yambol - Elhovo road after the junction to Boyanovo	R14	20.23	37	0	0.00	0.00
BG1IS00416MS049	Springs of Zlatna River	R15	10.48	60	54	0.90	0.86
BG1OS07112MS100	Karst Spring of Maarata - Krushina	R15	10.84	60	17	0.28	0.26
BG2VE08633MS425	Aidere River - Stoilovo village	R15	0.52	53	47	0.89	0.84
BG2PR211MS002	Devnenska River - estuary	R15	25.34	53	17	0.32	0.30
BG4ST00622MS900	Petrovska River, before estuary	R15	3.34	22	15	0.68	0.63
BG2RE00219MS497	Silistar River - before inflow into Black Sea (estuary)	R16	3.00	85	74	0.87	0.81
BG2RE92529MS496	Butamiyata River- estuary	R16	8.62	85	86	1.01	1.00

SiteCode	SiteName	WBType	PI	Ref	TsBRI	EQR	nEQR
BG2VE111MS001	Veleka River – Sinemorets village	R16	0.34	85	80	0.94	0.91
BG2IU00081MS254	Lisovo Dere River (Izgrevska Dere) - estuary, Tsarevo	R16	26.72	85	18	0.21	0.19
BG2IU6915MS002	Karaagach River - estuary	R16	9.47	85	84	0.99	0.99
BG2SE00219MS228	Fandakliyska River - estuary	R16	19.67	85	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ST06564MS403	Slavova River - river water intake	R01		72	61	0.85	0.79
BG4ST65141MS750	Sandanska Bistritsa River, before estuary	R03		82	52	0.63	0.58
BG1IS00061MS150	Lesnovska River, before inflow into Iskar River	R04		79	45	0.57	0.53
BG1IS04229MS1290	Bebresh River in Skravena village (after the low bridge)	R04		79	73	0.92	0.89
BG3MA05213MS0570	Chepelarska River, the bridge of Kemera	R05		90	77	0.86	0.80
BG4ME47319MS409	Mesta River, second bridge near Gospodnitsi village	R05		75	72	0.96	0.94
BG4ST00631MS320	Struma River near the boarder (bridge for Topolnitsa village)	R05		75	72	0.96	0.94
BG1VT00015MS020	Vit River, after Dolna Mitropoliya, near Bivolare village, 100m after the bridge	R07		78	77	0.99	0.99
BG2MA06931MS370	r. Sredetska – bridge to v.Valchanovo	R11		85	20	0.24	0.22
BG2PR00033MS003	r. Provadiyska – v. Sindel	R11		85	61	0.72	0.67
BG2SE00061MS005	r. Hadjiiska – v. Tankovo	R11		85	68	0.80	0.74
BG3MA00583MS0698	Potoka River before Saedinenie	R13		40	37	0.93	0.90
BG3AR00003MS0003	Bridge between the city of Ivailovgrad and v. Svirachi	R14		37	12	0.32	0.30
BG2IU07211MS404	Ropotamo River - before estuary, bridge on E 87	R16		85	31	0.36	0.33
BG2SE81MS008	Aheloy River - Camping Aheloy	R16		85	78	0.92	0.80
BG3TU00999MS0380	Tundzha River, Panitsite area, summer camp	R03				naturally no fish	NA
BG1YN00021MS020	Studena River, before inflow into Yantra River - road bridge	R08				naturally no fish	NA
BG1DJ00042MS040_1	r. Chairluk at v. Cherkovna	R09				naturally no fish	NA
BG1DJ00042MS040_2	r. Tsaratsar near the v. Golyama Voda	R09				naturally no fish	NA
BG1DJ00989MS1023	r. Suha downstream Odrintsy Dam	R09				naturally no fish	NA
BG1DJ09942MS090	r. Dobrichka at v. Rosenovo	R09				naturally no fish	NA
BG1DJ09994MS1010	r. Karaman at v. Mirovtsi	R09				naturally no fish	NA
BG4ST65312MS401	Upstream delta, v. Drakata	R14				naturally no fish	NA
BG4ST65334MS401	Vrabcha, upstream delta at E79 road before the town of Strumyani	R14				naturally no fish	NA
BG4ST65371MS720	r. Ludata at Yanovski bridge after Senokos site	R14				naturally no fish?	NA?
BG2VE08671MS426	Dokuzak River - after Malko Tarnovo, before the estuary, road for Stoilovo	R15				naturally no fish	NA

9.6 CLASSIFICATION RESULTS FOR LAKES

SiteCode	SiteName	WBType	PI	Ref	BFBILE	EQR	nEQR
BG3MA04629MS0451	Svezhen Reservoir	L13	12	100	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ME0000NMS003	Bez bog Lake	L01	1	100	92	0.92	0.92
BG4ST0000NMS001	Stoikovtsi Reservoir	L13	17	100	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ME02661MS914	Shiroka Polyana Reservoir - village zone	L03	12	100	68	0.68	0.80
BG3MA09549MS1510	Belmeken Reservoir	L03	7	100	74	0.74	0.84
BG4ME47382MS815	Kremensko ezero	L01	4	100	79	0.79	0.79
BG4ME47382MS815	Kremensko ezero	L01	3	100	79	0.79	0.79
BG1YN92233MS051	Hristo Smirnenski Reservoir	L02	11	100	18	0.18	0.14
BG3TU00077MS0220	Zhrebchevo Reservoir-wall	L11	14	100	54	0.54	0.50
BG1VT00032MS041	Telish Reservoir	L16	20	100	0	0.00	0.00
BG4L06MENA001_EEA	Riparian Wetlands	L06	9	100	70	0.70	0.80
BG3MA92259MS1410	Batak Reservoir	L03	13	100	0	0.00	0.00
BG4ME02661MS915	Shiroka Polyana Reservoir	L03	10	100	48	0.48	0.60
BG4ST65349MS825	Gergiisko Lake	L01	1	100	74	0.74	0.74
BG1IS22919MS031	Bebresh Reservoir	L02	10	100	85.5	0.86	0.80
BG3L06MANA003_EEA	Protected Area Zlato pole	L06	7	100	60	0.60	0.70
BG1OG00739MS031	Ogosta Reservoir	L14	16	100	17	0.17	0.23
BG1YN06496MS061	Yastrebino Reservoir	L12	15	100	39	0.39	0.34
BG2SE90000MS022	Burgas Lake- west	L08	13	90	34	0.38	0.44
BG2SE90000MS024	Burgas Lake - east	L08	13	90	44	0.49	0.55
BG4ME00292MS905	Dospat Reservoir-wall	L11	14	100	2	0.02	0.02
BG1VT00891MS051	Sopot Reservoir	L12	15	100	74	0.74	0.69
BG1YN43199MS021	Al. Stamboliyski Reservoir	L11	16	100	17	0.17	0.14
BG2DO10000MS007	Lake Shabla	L07	7	90	90	1.00	1.00
BG1IS69539MS041	Ognyanovo Reservoir	L02	17	100	40	0.40	0.35
BG3MA18739MS0071	Trakiets Reservoir	L15	14	100	34	0.34	0.29

BG4L06MENA001_EEA	Riparian Wetlands	L06	9	100	70	0.70	0.80
BG3MA00545MS0640	Piasachnik Reservoir	L15	20	100	47	0.47	0.42
BG3MA06481MS0740	Golyam Beglik Reservoir	L03	8	100	28.5	0.29	0.41
BG1W003496MS031	Rabisha Reservoir	L04A	9	50	0	0.00	0.00
BG1OG00744MS041	Srechenska Bara Reservoir	L16	8	100	25.5	0.26	0.32
BG2IU00061MS258	Dyavolsko Marsh	L08	15	90	17	0.19	0.25
BG3MA00631MS0720	Vacha Reservoir	L13	9	100	74	0.74	0.80
BG2IU10000MS004	Lake Alepu, from the shore	L08	7	90	67	0.74	0.80
BG4ST00691MS805	Choklyovo blato	L04B	9	40	47	1.00	1.00
BG3MA00338MS7269	Chirpan Reservoir	L17	18	60	0	0.00	0.00
BG1IS94733MS071	Beli Iskar Reservoir	L01	6	100	100	1.00	1.00
BG4ST65891MS815	Chernoto Lake	L01	2	100	85	0.85	0.85
BG1YN06295MS180	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-tail	L02	15	100	35	0.35	0.30
BG1OG00739MS031	Ogosta Reservoir	L14	14	100	17	0.17	0.23
BG1YN62953MS041	Yovkovtsi Reservoir-wall	L02	14	100	60	0.60	0.55
BG2IU20000MS257	lake Stamopolu	L08	8	90	34	0.38	0.44
BG3MA02191MS0116	Rozov Kladenets Reservoir	L15	16	100	0	0.00	0.00
BG2DO10000MS483	Lake Ezeretsko	L07	7	90	90	1.00	1.00
BG3AR00133MS0020	Ivaylovgrad Reservoir - wall	L11	14	100	84	0.84	0.80
BG3TU05239MS0040	Malko Sharkovo Reservoir	L13	15	100	32	0.32	0.38
BG2MA10000MS007	dam Mandra - iztok	L07	19	90	27	0.30	0.30
BG2KA47399MS020	Kamchia Reservoir	L11	8	100	10	0.10	0.08
BG1L04NVHM001_EEA	Dragoman Marsh	L04B	9	40	10	0.25	0.25
BG3MA03742MS0322	General Nikolaevo Reservoir-1	L17	19	60	not applicable		NA
BG2KA08471MS261	Fisek Reservoir	L12	19	100	not applicable		NA
BG2SE08331MS028	Aheloy Reservoir	L16	18	100	not applicable		NA
BG3MA00324MS1239	Garvanovo Reservoir	L15	24	100	not applicable		NA
BG3MA03929MS0371	Sushitsa Reservoir	L17	17	60	not applicable		NA
BG3MA03143MS1226	Byalo Pole Reservoir	L17	25	60	not applicable		NA
BG3L06MANA002_EEA	Krairechna Murtvitsa Lake near v. Popovitsa	L06	11	100	NA		NA

BG1VT00325MS031	Gorni Dabnik Reservoir	L14	22	100	not applicable	NA
BG1YN04471MS031	Krapets Reservoir	L12	18	100	not applicable	NA
BG2KA00233MS037	Eleshnitsa Reservoir	L12	13	100	not applicable	NA
BG4ST06963MS945	Dolna Dikanya Reservoir	L13	16	100	not applicable	NA
BG3AR00086MS0290	Smolianski Lakes (Trevisto Lake)	L03	6	100	NA	NA
BG3MA00347MS0280	Mechka Reservoir	L17	18	60	not applicable	NA
BG3MA00225MS0120	Ovcharitsa Reservoir	L15	28	100	not applicable	NA
BG1W000814MS071	Rasovo Reservoir	L16	26	100	not applicable	NA
BG2SE98935MS263	Troyanovo Reservoir	L16	19	100	not applicable	NA
BG2KA47379MS488	Skala 1 Reservoir	L04A	14	50	not applicable	NA

